

The Images of the Field for Cramming Education and General Education Constructed by the Vending Performance Form

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Vending Performance Form

- The exist mode in the vending field which have performance function.
- The characteristics positioning of non-traditional construction technique/approach.
- Focusing on the exist morphology of the field itself.

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Attempts

- Taking the Vending Performance Form as theoretical approach.
- Gaze the industry in education culture and the culture in education industry.
- Construct the images of education field for realizing and narrative.

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Research Methodology

- Explaining and recounting the status quo bases on the Phenomenology
- Vending Performance Form is background theory as perspective to realize 2 major orientation/aspect of education.
- Two kinds of education field: the field of cramming education and the field of general education.

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Research Method

- The fieldwork in high school education and the cramming education (the subjects of English and Mathematics) in central Taiwan.
- The study time in fieldwork is about two years.
- Taking observations and records as the text for analyzing and discussing after.

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The Field of Cramming Education

- Economic characteristics changing and extending toward the business strategy in strong commercialization.
- Performing the individual value by the knowledge merchandising in education process.
- Performativity in the physical explicit appearance.

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The Field of General Education

- Take performance as fundamental of field shaping instead of economic characteristics.
- Put culture in the position which is more emphasize the subjectivity when discussing in culture and economics of education.
- Economic consciousness is implicated in the performance of the knowledge merchandising form and the highly knowledge density providing.

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Images of the Field Constructed

- Intersectionality presents in the interaction of vending field and performance function between two subjects.
- The possibility of agency enhancing in education field is utterance.
- The images can be taken as a strategy to operate and adjust the connection or the relation of two or more different subjectivity in education.

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販售形式構建的補習教育與普通教育場域圖像

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販售形式 (Vending Performance Form) 是對於具有展演功能的販售場域中形塑出的存在樣態，針對場域本身存在的形貌透過非傳統構框手法做出的特性定位。本文試圖以販售形式作為理論取徑 (theoretical approach) 凝視教育現場裡「教育文化中的產業」與「教育產業中的文化」，並且透過將販售形式的理論背景作為視角以理解教育的二大面向為出發，對臺灣補習教育場域 (the field of cramming education) 及普通教育場域 (the field of general education) 中現象的表達進行詮釋與論述，構建用以理解及敘說教育場域的圖像。

本文透過現象學 (Phenomenology) 的研究法 (research methodology) 詮釋在當前中學教育裡，補習教育及普通教育二種面向的現狀敘事。在研究方法 (research method) 上，基本上主要以臺灣中部某地區的高級中學教育現場和某補習班的高中數學及英文課程作為田野調查的場所。透過大約兩年的田野調查，在實務材料上，做出在教學現場針對教師的教學過程所進行的觀察與記錄，而這些從教育現場取得的資料是為後續販售理論分析的文本以及販售理論對話的對象。

補習教育之中以產業自身本質具備的經濟性 (economic characteristics) 變動並延展出強烈傾向商業化 (Commercialization) 的經營策略作為場域主體的特徵定調，而在其中教學者的教育過程則是經由知識銷售 (knowledge merchandising) 的形式表現個體價值，以及物理性外觀樣貌在補習教育場域中的展演性 (Performativity)。相對於補習教育，普通教育更傾向以教學過程的展演作為場域形塑的基調，在文化與經濟面向的對話中，學校教師會將文化放在主體性更強烈的位置，其中學校教師作為教學者，位處於文化定位較強的教學互動之中，經濟性的意識隱含在販賣學識作為表現的形式裡，教育的確切意涵上實質內容面向的密度供給。整體而言，根據販售形式中展演功能及販售場域的交織性 (Intersectionality) 進行二主體間的互動論述，表達了在教育場域之中能動性增強 (agency enhancing) 的可能，而位於形式層面的本質化導向論述則是構建了補習教育及普通教育二類場域的圖像。經由販售形式構建出的圖像，可以作為理解與凝視當前臺灣教育場域的工具，同時亦是操作及調整教育中不同主體間連結關係的策略取向。

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